

UNIVERSITY OF BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

BB-2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

**CASE ANALYSIS: THE ADOPTION OF AYESHA'S FARM USING HARVARD
MODEL**

2ND INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT

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Executive summary

This report will discuss Ayesha's farm, determine and analyze the issues and provide alternative solutions that can improve their business. The farm is a home based hydroponic business that was founded in 2017 by Aedy Ashryn Bin Haji Matali and his wife, Wizna. In the course of their business journey, they have been struggling with the issues that arise mainly with the limited space and capital in need to do their farming. Under case analysis will discuss the harvard model system which is a soft hrm model system designed to focus on the well being and commitment of employees. There are two types of harvard system that will be discussed in this report and they are the harvard framework and human resource system. Moreover, under Alternative solutions are solutions that can be beneficial and opportunity wise for Ayesha's farm. Overall, to conclude the report, it will be discussed the cons of the solutions and in recommendations are the recommended solutions that Aedy should consider for Ayesha's farm.

Introduction

Ayesha's farm is a home based hydroponics business located in Perumahan Lugu. It was founded in 2017 by Aedy Ashryn Bin Haji Matali and his wife, Wizna bte Anuar. Ayesha's farm focuses on selling vegetables that are specially grown using hydroponic methods as well as hydroponic sets that are suitable for any household or personal use. The farm also offers farming lessons to young children to get more exposure with agriculture. The objective of this report is to determine and analyze the issues of Ayesha's farm and provide alternative solutions that can improve their business.

Problem statement

1.1 young startup business

Ayesha's farm is still a young business and requires a lot of growing in order to expand the business.

1.2 Limited time to consume in the business

As mentioned in the book, Aedy has time constraints as he can only focus on the business late in the evenings and during weekends.

1.3 Limited Space

As use his backyard to farm, there is not enough space to grow and build hydroponic sets at their home.

1.4 Limited Capital

Aedy mentioned that money can be an issue as hydroponics require a lot of needs such as water, fertilizers and electricity.

Case analysis

2.1 the harvard model system

The Harvard system model is a soft HRM model designed by the Harvard school of Beer et al (1984) and it is one of the most influential models in the HRM that focuses on the outcome for people, their well-being and organization commitment. This model views employees as a major role in the business to those who have their own interest and are willing to commit their work to the company.

The harvard system model can also be identified as a means of agreeing on the plans and objectives of a company that reflects at both the relationship between employment and the following human resource management processes and processes within an organization –

development, recruitment, training, employee benefit and relationship strategies, performance management, policies and procedures.

There are **two types** of harvard model system which are:

- **The harvard framework** includes the stakeholder interest, situational factors, HRM policies choice, HR outcomes and long term consequences
- **Human resource system** includes employee influence, reward systems, work systems and human resource flow

2.2 the harvard framework

The Harvard framework

When making the HRM policy decisions, managers are required to consider the four C's which are commitment, competence, congruence and cost effectiveness. The Harvard model focuses on the attention on the outcomes of the people especially the well being and organisational commitment.

According to Digitaltech (n.d.), there are six components in the harvard model system which are:

2.2.1 Stakeholder interest

In this component, it includes all the shareholders, management, employee groups , governments and unions. These interests are the ones that define the HRM policies.

2.2.2 Situational factors

This component consists of situations that could influence the policies. The factors include workforce characteristics, unions, business strategy and conditions, management philosophy, labour market, task technology and laws and social values.

2.2.3 HRM policies

HRM policies are influenced by situational factors and stakeholder interest. In this component it includes the core human resource activities such as recruitment, training and reward systems.

2.3.4 HRM Outcomes

HRM outcomes is when the component is done well, it can lead to either good or bad outcomes. This includes commitment, cost- effectiveness, commitment and congruence.

2.3.5 Long- term consequences

Under this component, when hrm outcomes are positive, it can lead to long term consequences. It includes individual well- being, organizational effectiveness and social well-being.

2.3 Human Resource System

In 1985, Richard Walton published an article in the Harvard Business Review called 'From Control to Workplace Engagement,' which popularized soft HRM as an unique approach to human resource management. His statement was that efficient HRM does not rely on workforce management strategies, but on performance management approaches.

The human resource system proposed that much of the complex personnel and labour rights strategies can be dealt with in four areas in human resources (HR) which are:

2.3.1 Employee influence

Employee influence can be how much of responsibility, authority and power that is assigned on a moral level to management and to whom. In this section, it is determined how management shares their influence and to what extent they can create compatibility of interest between the management and employees.

2.3.2 Reward systems

Reward systems regulate how employees' services are rewarded whether it is extrinsic or intrinsic. In extrinsic rewards, it can be rewards such as tangible pay or benefits such as overtime pay, bonuses, profit sharing, pensions, holiday pay, flexible working hours and more. Intrinsic rewards are rewards from the commitment and motivation of the employee itself such as achievements, self confidence, self-esteem, satisfaction, challenges and involvement. In the human resource system, it is best that employees should be highly involved with all the work including the design of the organization's reward systems. It is also best to observe the best decisions for these employees besides meeting their needs as the organization must also be consistent with the business strategy, management philosophy and other HRM policies.

2.3.3 Work systems

Work systems are the strategies for organizing whether in people, information, activities or technologies at all levels of the organization in order to achieve a better performance efficiently and effectively.

Alternative solutions

3.1 young start up business

As Aedy mentioned in the problem statement, that their business is still young and new. Here are some ways to help gain more exposure to the business as well as gaining new customers.

3.1.1 Market more

By marketing more, the business can earn more exposure and can gain more customers who are interested in hydroponics. Marketing can also gain valuable insight through 'social listening' meaning listening to what customers want and gaining insight on their behavior as well as what appeals to the target market so they can improve the business. Marketing can be simply using social media as it does not cost any capital by signing up and creating a profile for free for all social networking platforms. If Aedy decides to use paid advertising on social media, it is also cost efficient as you can adjust how much you are willing to spend.

3.1.2 Host or participate in events

By hosting and joining events such as joining exhibitions or giving classes outside of home or even giving talks on how to maintain a hydroponics can give more exposure to the business. It also helps to gain more new customers as well as gaining customer's loyalty and building relationships with them.

3.2 limited time

Aedy stated that he was only able to focus on the business at a limited time.

3.2.1 hire or get volunteers

By involving volunteers that are interested in the same field can help them learn and achieve not only their objectives but also to achieve in the sultan's titah by diversifying our economy in helping to develop the agriculture industry and to gain interest in the younger generation. By involving volunteers can help the business to engage more in diverse range of skills, experience and knowledge. Volunteering can also help relationships within the community and contribute in supporting others who have the same objectives as Ayesha's farm. It also helps to bring in more ideas and opinions to the business where businesses can adapt and identify what they can improve on doing.

3.3 limited capital

3.3.1 Get investment allowances from agriculture and agrifood department

According to the agriculture and agrifood department website, it is possible to apply investment allowances in order to help businesses like Ayesha's farm.

“ Where a company proposes to carry out a project, the investment allowance granted for the approved project shall be a specified percentage not exceeding 100% of the amount of fixed capital expenditure incurred on each item specified on an approved project if the fixed capital expenditure is incurred :

- Within such period, not exceeding 5 years, commencing from the investment day
- In the case of the promotion of the tourist industry, not exceeding 11 years commencing from the investment day.”

3.3.2 Co-matching scheme from Dare Enterprise

Co Matching scheme is a grant to help assist businesses in starting up or expanding their business. It is a finance scheme that can grant up to \$bnd 20,000 maximum.

According to the Dare Enterprise, there are two categories of the Co-Matching Scheme and they are:

There are **2 categories** of Co-Matching Scheme:

1. Starting Up

In start ups, it is applicable for new businesses registered within (not more than) twelve (12) months. In this scheme it is targeted in assisting the starting up of innovative startups. DARE will fund 70% (up to B\$10,000) of the total project cost.

2. Expansion

In this scheme, it is applicable for established businesses registered more than twelve (12) months. It is targeted at businesses looking to expand their businesses to the next level such as to increase productivity, expand range of products or services or looking into expanding internationally. DARE is willing to fund 70% (up to B\$20,000) of the total project cost.

To be eligible for the co matching scheme, businesses/companies have to satisfy the following general eligibility criteria:

- Must be registered and based in Brunei Darussalam (100% locally owned businesses by Citizens or Permanent Residents)
- Product/services offered must be locally owned.
- Must be able to match at least 30% of total project cost, with prior experience in securing investment considered to be advantageous.

1. Criteria for Starting Up

- Must fall within definition of micro or small enterprises i.e. have fewer than 20 employees
 - Must be currently participating or accomplished one of DARE's Bootcamp Programmes (e.g. Accelerate or Micro Bootcamp)

2. Criteria for Expansion

- Must fall within the definition of micro, small or medium enterprises i.e. have fewer than 100 employees
- Must practice proper book-keeping, and able to provide applicable financial records
- For Sole Proprietorship or Partnership, businesses are strongly encouraged to convert the status of their existing business into Sendirian Berhad (Sdn Bhd)

Conclusion

In conclusion, Ayesha's farm is a home based hydroponic business founded in 2017 by Aedy Ashryn and his wife, Wizna. In the course of doing their business, they have been struggling with problems such as limited capital, space as well as time in spending into the business. The Harvard model system is a soft hrn model used to focus on people's commitment and wellbeing. By applying the model, Ayesha's farm will be able to gain more income to the family business as well as earning and building relationships with customers that may be interested to work or associate with Ayesha's farm.

Recommendation

Aedy should apply the co matching scheme. It will not only help to grow Ayesha's farm but also enable it to bring in more resources with the help of Dare. This will also help them to invest more into the business, increasing their motivation and work more to bring in more profit and resources to the business. This will also help them to grow more products to enable them to sell more and distribute to shops.

Aedy should also focus on expanding their business by giving more exposure. By participating in events, Aedy can learn more and be able to meet new customers and build relationships with other agripreneurs. Marketing in social media can also earn the business exposure and it only requires little or no capital at all. Social media can help to gain more new customers and easy to connect with them.

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